

is used as the titrant. Furthermore, while determining the acid content of a product containing a component capable of reacting with alkali, the titration with alkali cannot yield correct results. For example, in estimating carboxy acids in lac, the resin present undergoes saponification⁶. In certain products which are slightly coloured the neutralization indicators may not be very suitable. For these reasons attempts were made^{4,5} to evolve an iodometric method for the estimation of weak acids—but these attempts had limited applicability and were time consuming. Kolthoff's modified procedure⁵ has been adopted by several workers⁷⁻⁹ for estimating the acid content in a number of products, but the time required for the completion of the reaction is 2-24 hours. The proposed procedure is simple, rapid and accurate; being iodometric it possesses sharp end-point, the amounts of reagent and reaction time are not critical and hence it can be adopted with advantage for the titrimetric determination of dilute solutions of weak acids.

TABLE 1—IODOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF CERTAIN ORGANIC ACIDS
(Room Temperature 30-35°)

Sl. No.	Acids	KIO ₃ , KI added		Reaction time (mins)	% Deviation*	
		(g)	(g)		Proposed method	Comparison method**
1.	Formic	1	2	2	0.1	0.5
2.	Acetic	2	2	5	0.2	0.6
3.	Monochloroacetic	0.5	0.5	2	0.2	0.6
4.	Dichloroacetic	0.5	0.5	2	0.1	0.5
5.	Trichloroacetic	0.5	0.5	2	0.2	0.7
6.	Propionic	2	5	5	0.4	0.9
7.	β -chloropropionic	1	2	2	0.3	0.8
8.	Butyric	2	5	5	0.5	0.9
9.	Oxalic	1	1	2	0.2	0.6
10.	Malonic	2	5	10	0.3	0.7
11.	Succinic	2	5	10	0.5	0.9
12.	Glycollic	1	2	5	0.2	0.8
13.	Malic	1	1	2	0.2	0.7
14.	Tartaric	1	1	2	0.4	0.6
15.	Citric	1	1	5	0.3	0.7
16.	Crotonic	1	2	5	0.2	0.6

* Average of six determinations.

** In these titrations phenolphthalein colour faded rapidly. The first appearance of red colour was taken as the end-point.

In case of acids 3, 4 and 5 iodide and iodate solutions can also be employed. In case of acid 10, the reaction-time should not exceed 15 mins otherwise low results are obtained.

Table 1 shows the amount of potassium iodide and potassium iodate to be added and reaction time to be allowed in case of sixteen acids examined. A comparative study of determination of these acids at micro level (0.05 meq. of acid present in 10 ml of assay solution) by iodometry and alkalimetry has also been presented in this table. The concentration of the titrant solution (sodium thiosulphate or sodium hydroxide) used was 0.005N.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Professor G. S. Misra, Dean, Faculty of Science, University of Jabalpur, Jabalpur for providing facilities for this work. One of the authors (S.N.N.) acknowledges financial assistance from the University of Jabalpur, Jabalpur.

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Polarographic Study of Ni(II)-Succinimide System

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Manuscript received 2 January 1979, revised 18 September 1979, accepted 9 April 1980

A survey of the literature reveals that although the behaviour of Ni(II) in presence of various complexing media has been investigated but very few studies have been reported with amides^{1,2}. Ni(II)-succinimide system has not been investigated so far. It was, therefore, thought worthwhile to study the polarographic behaviour of Ni(II) in the presence of succinimide.

Experimental

Ni(NO₃)₂.6H₂O was used as the source for depolarizer metal ion, Ni(II). Supporting electrolyte was KCl. The potassium salt of succinimide was prepared from succinimide and KOH. All the chemicals used were of high purity (B.D.H or S. Merck) and all the solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water. In the final polarographic

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solution the Ni(II) concentration was kept as 1 mM. The concentration of succinimide was varied by adding different amounts of the stock solution of potassium-succinimide. The pH of the final solution was maintained by adding a dilute solution of NaOH. A manual polarograph in conjunction with a polyflex galvanometer was used to record polarograms. Deoxygenation of the solution was done by passing nitrogen gas. The dropping mercury electrode consisted of a standard capillary (E. H. Sargent & Co., USA) and had following characteristics: $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.8446 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/2}$, $t = 3.48 \text{ sec}$. in 0.5M KCl at -1.3 V vs S.C.E., $h_{\text{corr}} = 63.3 \text{ cm}$. Slope and $E_{1/2}$ values have been calculated by least square method from $E_{\text{a.e.}}$ vs $\log i/i_a - i$ plots.

Results and Discussion

The linearity of the plots of i_d vs \sqrt{h} reveals the diffusion controlled nature of the system. The irreversible nature of the electrode reaction is established by the slope values and also from $\log i$ vs $\log h$ plots³. For a totally irreversible process the current at the foot of the wave should be independent of the height of the mercury column while the limiting current should be proportional to \sqrt{h} . Between the two extremes both diffusion and kinetics of the electrode reaction affect the current. At various stages of a polarogram, starting from the "foot" to "levelling off" positions $\log i$ - $\log h$ plots were straight lines with slope varying from 0 to 0.5.

It was observed that the variation of the concentration of the ligand affected the pH of the resultant solution. Therefore, to ensure that the shift in $E_{1/2}$ was solely due to the complexation and not due to pH change resulting from different concentrations of ligand, it was found necessary to maintain pH.

A solution of 1 mM Ni(II) without any potassium succinimide had pH 5.9. Addition of 0.04M potassium succinimide altered the pH to 6.8. Attempt to increase pH beyond pH 8 resulted in turbidity. No shift in $E_{1/2}$ was observed at pH 6. This allowed only a very small range of pH. Maximum shift which signifies maximum stability of complex was observed at pH 8.

TABLE 1

Conc. of Ni(II)	Conc. of ligand M	pH	$-E_{1/2}$ V vs S.C.E.	$\Delta E_{1/2}$
1 mM	0.00	7.0	1.010	0.150
	0.04		0.860	
1 mM	0.00	8.0	1.010	0.180
	0.04		0.830	

Kinetics of the electrode process as a function of ligand concentration was studied at pH 8. α_{na} values showed an increase up to the ligand concentration of

0.6 mM and then decreased. An attempt to estimate n_a apparently leads to a conclusion that $n_a = 2$ because for totally irreversible systems, as the present one is, α should be less than 0.5. However, according to Meites⁴ only a single electron can be transferred at a time and a value of n_a exceeding 1 should merely mean that the successive steps are too nearly simultaneous to be distinguished on the time scale implicit in the polarographic measurement. Thus whether n_a is 1 or 2 the change in α_{na} values which at no stage vary by a factor of 2 between successive values can only be due to change in α . Increase in α values signifies shift towards reversibility. Thus it may be concluded that the Ni(II)-succinimide complex is reduced more easily than the aqueous Ni(II) ion⁵ which is in conformity with other ligands in case of Ni(II).

Decrease in α_{na} values between 0.08-0.1M potassium-succinimide concentration could not be explained for the moment, however, it was in conformity with negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ with increase in ligand concentration beyond certain limits as observed by other workers⁶ in case of other ligands.

TABLE 2

$\mu = 0.5$, pH = 8.0, Temp. = $25 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$

[Succinimide] M	$-E_{1/2}$ V vs S.C.E.	Slope	α_{na}
0.00	1.045	0.115	0.5141
0.01	0.910	0.100	0.5915
0.02	0.900	0.100	0.5915
0.04	0.895	0.095	0.6220
0.06	0.900	0.095	0.6220
0.08	0.910	0.100	0.5915
1.00	0.910	0.100	0.5915

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to the Principal, Agra College, Agra for providing necessary facilities and Dr. Mukhtar Singh for his interest in the work.

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